

conditions are altered. We found that isolates from both copepods favor an alkaline pH, temperatures ranging from 28-35°C, a low salinity concentration of 0.85‰, and peptone as nitrogen source. These results reveal that *Aeromonas* are capable of degrading chitin using both organic and inorganic carbon source and in a wide range of pH and temperature, suggesting that the different species of this group of bacteria easily adapt to the environmental changes in the lake, allowing them to produce chitin-degrading enzymes even under unfavorable conditions.

This study was able to show the presence of chitinoclastic *Aeromonas* on copepods present in Lake Taal. Although we have not fully identified the bacterial community for each copepod species, we believe that this study can influence other researchers to further explore the bacterial community of copepod species in Philippine lakes. To our knowledge this microbiological study is the first to be done for copepods in Lake Taal, and this would not have been possible without the aid of the Tonolli Memorial Fund.

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Effect of zooplankton, macrophytes and piscivorous fish in the control of *Microcystis* spp. (cyanobacteria): mesocosm experiments

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Cyanobacterial blooms are one of the main problems in urban water bodies, especially when these are refilled using partially treated wastewater as is the case for several ponds, lakes and canals in Mexico City (Figueroa-Sánchez *et al.*, 2014; 2020). These blooms affect the water quality, aquatic biota and the people who use these sites for recreation. This is the case in the rowing and canoeing canal "Virgilio Uribe" (RCC) an artificial, eutrophic water body (Gayosso-Morales *et al.* 2018) affected by *Microcystis* blooms throughout the year. The canal provides refuge to migratory or partially migratory birds such pelicans, storks and coots. The canal also has a small colony of the endemic but highly endangered Axolotl (*Ambystoma*

a mixture of the green algae *Chlorella vulgaris* and *Scenedesmus acutus* for more than a year before experimentation.

Typha latifolia was available in the RCC. Juvenile stage macrophytes (1.5 m) extracted from the root were washed and used. Subsequently, the plants were placed in 20 L containers with RCC water previously filtered through a 90 µm mesh size. All the above was carried out 48 h before setting up the experiment. *Goodea atripinnis* (1.5 ± 0.05 cm total length) were captured from the RCC using homemade traps made with PET (1 L) nasa-type bottles. The fish were kept in a 20 L tank containing unfiltered water from the RCC. The fish were fed *S. cf mixtus* every 2 days prior to experimentation. *Petenia splendida* (14±1cm), a piscivorous fish were acquired from Acuapets aquaculture fish farm in the State of Tabasco and transferred to Mexico City.

For both experiments sixteen cylindrical aluminum frames covered with transparent polyethylene to form closed containers (45 cm diameter, 60cm length and 80L capacity) were employed (Figure 1). Each was filled with 70 L of previously filtered (mesh size 200 and 90 µm) water from the site. Mixed population of *S. cf mixtus* (5 ind./ L) was added to the mesocosms from a previously established laboratory culture. A bunch of *T. latifolia* (600 g) was added to the treatments (T). We also introduced three individuals of *G. atripinnis* (2 cm) previously

Fig. 1 Mesocosm set up in the RCC and the first author at the study site.

mexicanum), and the native acocil crayfish.

Research on biomanipulation in tropical and subtropical systems is relatively new. For the RCC, we hypothesized that the abundance of the cladoceran *Simocephalus*, a crustacean species capable of surviving on *Microcystis* (Nandini and Rao, 1998) will increase in the absence of the omnivorous fish *Goodea atripinnis* (Goodeidae), while the presence of the macrophyte *Typha latifolia* will provide shelter to the cladoceran against fish predation and promote the decrease of nutrients, resulting in a decrease in cyanobacteria. On the other hand, the abundance of *Simocephalus* would increase in the presence of the piscivorous fish *Petenia splendida* due to its predation on *Goodea atripinnis*.

To test this, we isolated *Simocephalus cf mixtus* from a canal in Lake Xochimilco and cultured them in 30L containers in aerated tap water and

captured from the site. In treatments with the piscivorous fish, one *P. splendida* (Ps) (14±1cm) per container was introduced. Four replicates per treatment were set up. The mesocosms were placed inside the canal, firmly tied so as to avoid tilting from wind or wave action. Observations and sampling were carried out for 16 days.

Zooplankton species were quantified; cladocerans were counted and subsequently returned to each treatment while rotifers and copepods were filtered using a mesh of 50 µm and fixed in 4% formalin for later analysis. *Microcystis* spp. were quantified as individuals or colonies per ml. For both sets of experiments, chlorophyll (Figure 2), largely contributed by *Microcystis* sp. declined with the presence of *Simocephalus* and *Typha*. The presence of fish, omnivores or piscivores, resulted in a decline in the cladoceran density and thereby an increase

Fig. 2. Chlorophyll a concentration of experiment 1 and 2 in the different treatments with *Simocephalus cf mixtus* (Sm), *Typha latifolia* (Ti), *Goodea atripinnis* (Ga) and *Petelia splendida* (Ps) during the established period.

Fig. 3. Population density of *Simocephalus cf mixtus* in the different treatments with *Simocephalus cf mixtus* (Sm), *Typha latifolia* (Ti), *Goodea atripinnis* (Ga) and *Petelia splendida* (Ps) during the established experimentation period in 2018 (A) and 2019 (B).

in the density of the cyanobacteria was observed (Figure 3).

Our study showed that mesocosms with cladocerans alone or with the macrophytes had a lower growth of cyanobacteria than did those that had piscivorous and/or planktivorous fish. The presence of *Simocephalus cf mixtus* resulted in a 60 to 80% decrease in chlorophyll a. *Simocephalus*, in this study, was adversely affected by fish, and our tests show that introducing piscivorous fish alone may not suffice to the control planktivorous fish in tropical systems; physical removal of fish, in addition to nutrient input controls, may be necessary to increase cladoceran density and reduce phytoplankton. Further studies are necessary to test the combined effect of piscivorous fish and macrophyte cover on the control of cyanobacteria.

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This year (2020) the Tonolli Committee has awarded Maite Colina (Uruguay) USD 1500 for her project to run a microcosm experiment exploring CO₂ uptake and carbon sedimentation in eutrophic warm conditions.

Lake Tarawera New Zealand
Photo by David Hamilton